

Braden Hale Bagley
Kevin A. Stein
Matthew H. Barton
Hayden V. Coombs

“No Excuses: An Empirical Case for Mortification
and Corrective Action”

No Excuses: An Empirical Case for Mortification and Corrective Action

Braden Hale Bagley¹
Kevin A. Stein²
Matthew H. Barton³
Hayden V. Coombs⁴

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to identify quantitatively which image repair strategies are perceived as the most effective, and in what ways mortification and corrective action strengthen an apology, by providing subscales for examination. A total of 534 participants responded to a survey and were randomly assigned to one of 14 groups aligning with one of 14 image repair strategies. An exploratory factor analysis resulted in five subscales, including learning, appropriateness, character, rectification, and sincerity. In nearly all instances, mortification and corrective action led to significantly stronger perceptions of apology. These two strategies are more forthright, open, and show a willingness to make change, and as a result are more palatable to audiences in most circumstances. On the contrary, strategies that attempt to justify, minimize or deflect blame, are easily discerned by audiences as weaker strategies, yet surprisingly, people continue to use them. Making more specific one-to-one connections between strategy and response can provide greater understanding for academics as well as practitioners about which image repair strategies fit best in unique cases.

137

Keywords

Image repair, scale, crisis, *apologia*, reputation

¹ Southern Utah University, Communication Department, USA, bradenbagley@suu.edu, ORCID: 0000-0002-2043-6333

² Southern Utah University, Communication Department, USA, stein@suu.edu, ORCID: 0009-0008-7689-3809

³ Southern Utah University, Communication Department, USA, bartonm@suu.edu, ORCID: 0009-0001-0806-0839

⁴ Brigham Young University Idaho, Department of Health and Recreation, USA, coombh@byui.edu, ORCID: 0000-0002-4800-2334

Introduction

In 1973, Ware and Linkugel formalized the idea of examining apology speeches as a unique family of discourse. Since that time, more than 500 articles and books have been published in the area of image repair and *apologia* studies. As this typology took root, other scholars worked to enhance a disciplinary understanding of *apologia* as a genre of discourse that ought to be examined more thoroughly. Chief among these scholars was William Benoit (1995a) who transformed the original scholarship into a 14-point typology of strategies for examining *apologia* rhetoric and the way it was used to repair public image. Of these strategies, mortification and corrective action have frequently been identified as two of the most useful approaches (Arendt et al., 2017; Benoit and Drew, 1997; Siew-Yoong Low et al., 2011). Mortification has been characterized as “rhetorical choices of honesty about the situation and related wrongdoing and acceptance of the consequences – among these a pledge to change future behavior” (Stein and Barton, 2019: 254). When using this strategy, the individual essentially takes full responsibility for a negative event or decision and expresses remorse for any negative outcome that resulted from the wrongdoing. Corrective action is often a follow-up strategy to mortification (although it can be used separately) and has been defined as “doing something to offset the perceived wrong that has been committed” (Benoit, 2016a: 30). However, the studies arguing that these two strategies are the most effective have been primarily qualitative in nature. The purpose of this paper is to add to these declarations using quantitative data. Secondly, this paper aims to identify in what ways these two approaches strengthen an apology, by providing subscales for examination.

Literature Review

Scholars have examined *apologia*/image repair discourse in a number of different contexts including:

- 1) Political: Studies have explored presidential rhetoric during campaigns (Benoit, 2017; Smith, 2017) as well as presidential responses to attacks while in office (Benoit, 1982; Benoit, 2016b; Benoit, 2019, Benoit, Gullifor, and Panici, 1991; Benoit and Henson, 2009; Blair, 1984; Harrell et al., 1975; Kramer and Olson, 2002; Simons, 2000; Theye, 2008). Other studies have examined political apologies by trusted insiders (Benoit and Anderson, 1996; Kahl, 1984) and congressional leaders (Kennedy and Benoit, 1997; Len-Rios and Benoit, 2004; Liu, 2008; Short, 1987).
- 2) Organizational: These studies have investigated *apologia* in a variety of industry and organizational contexts. For example, some have examined health-related consequences of corporate missteps (Benoit and Lindsey, 1987; Brinson and Benoit, 1996; Huxman and Bruce, 1995; Smith, 2012), customer inconvenience (Benoit and Brinson, 1994; Thomsen, 2023), trust (Benoit, 1995b; Compton, 2014; Hearit, 1999), and negligence (Benoit and Czerwinski, 1997; Harlow et al., 2011; Seeger and Ulmer, 2002).

- 3) International Relations: These studies have explored topics such as war crimes (Edwards, 2005; Tabak and Avraham, 2018), complicity during genocide (Edwards, 2008; Mueller II, 2004), encroachments into sovereign territory (Drumheller and Benoit, 2004; Stein, 2008; Zhang and Benoit, 2004), poor diplomacy (Stein et al., 2013), misleading news coverage (Handley, 2008), and contaminated or defective products (Peijuan et al., 2009; Wen et al., 2012).
- 4) Sports: These studies address various indiscretions by athletes and organizations, including doping/drugs (Walsh, McAllister-Spooner, 2011; Glantz, 2010; Sanderson and Hambrick, 2016), contract negotiations (Brazeal, 2008), mishandling Title IX cases (Riggs, 2019), physical assault (Benoit, 2018a; Benoit and Hanczor, 1994), sexual assault (Len-Ríos, 2010), infidelity (Nelson, 1984; Husselbee and Stein, 2012), falling for deception (Frederick et al., 2014), bullying (Schmittel and Hull, 2015), breaking game rules (Sheffer, Schultz, and Tubbs, 2018), and patriotic protest (Martin and McHendry Jr., 2016).
- 5) Media and Film: These studies have analyzed unethical journalism (Kaylor, 2010; Kauffman, 2018; Hindman, 2005), racism (Benoit, 2011; Kramer, 2013; Stein, 2010; Len-Ríos et al, 2015), sexism (Lauzen, 2016), sexual misconduct (Benoit, 1997; Wetherbee, 2019), public defamation (Kauffman, 2012; Moody, 2011; McGuire, 2012; Compton and Miller, 2011), and offensive cinematic content (Benoit and Nill, 1998; Stein et al., 2021).

The preceding studies are meant only to provide a sense of the volume of image repair research and not an attempt at an exhaustive list. The following review of literature focuses on mortification and corrective action, as they are central to the findings of the current study.

Mortification

Mortification is a vital image repair strategy that centers on the admission of wrongdoing and an apology to restore an individual's or organization's damaged reputation (Stein and Barton, 2018). As part of Benoit's broader theory of image repair, mortification stands out among five main strategies: denial, evasion of responsibility, reducing offensiveness, corrective action, and mortification (Benoit, 1995a; Benoit and Drew, 1997). What distinguishes mortification is that it involves the accused admitting guilt and seeking forgiveness, making it an effective approach for crises where responsibility is clear (Stein and Barton, 2019). Of all of the strategies, it is the most complete for apologizing, because it requires the apologizer to admit wrongdoing, show remorse (verbally or nonverbally), and specify a future course of action away from the problem.

Benoit (1995a) emphasizes that mortification includes two key components: expressions of regret and a plea for forgiveness. This strategy is particularly useful when the audience expects accountability, as acknowledging fault can meet public demands for responsibility (Benoit, 2018b). Moreover, Benoit highlights the importance of sincerity in apologies, suggesting that the perceived sincerity directly influences how effective the apology is. For instance, Brown (2016) found that mortification is especially impactful in cases of criminal transgressions involving athletes compared to non-criminal ones. Similarly, Stein and Barton (2019) examined the nuances of mortification, underscoring the role that

framing and delivery play in how an apology is received. They argue that a well-crafted apology, which fully acknowledges wrongdoing and avoids shifting blame, is more likely to be accepted by the public.

However, mortification is not without its limitations as the success of this strategy hinges on the nature of the crisis and, importantly, the audience's perception of sincerity (Benoit, 2018b). If the apology is perceived as insincere or manipulative, it can backfire, worsening the situation (Swanson, 2008). Despite these risks, when executed with genuine remorse, mortification remains a highly effective tool for restoring credibility and repairing reputations. Its effectiveness has been demonstrated across a variety of contexts, though success largely depends on the nature of the crisis and how the apology is perceived (Benoit and Drew, 1997; Brown, 2016; Stein and Barton, 2019).

Corrective Action

Corrective action is aimed at addressing and mitigating reputational damage by taking concrete steps to resolve a crisis and prevent its recurrence (Benoit, 1995a). Corrective action involves not only rectifying the immediate issue, but also ensuring that similar problems do not arise in the future (Benoit and Drew, 1997). This strategy signals responsibility, offering tangible solutions that go beyond mere apologies to restore trust and credibility (Benoit and Drew, 1997).

Corrective action is considered highly effective when the public or stakeholders demand accountability for an offense (Benoit, 2018c). Unlike denial or evasion of responsibility, this strategy demonstrates a proactive commitment to making amends and preventing future issues. For example, in the case of United Airlines, following the public relations crisis involving the forceful removal of a passenger, the company employed corrective action by revising its policies on customer treatment and overbooked flights (Benoit, 2018). This action not only addressed the immediate outrage, but also helped the company regain some of its lost trust by showing its willingness to prevent similar incidents.

The effectiveness of corrective action lies in its focus on solution-oriented measures, which allow organizations or individuals to rebuild their reputations through action rather than words alone (Benoit, 2018c). For instance, Peijuan et al. (2009) highlighted the Chinese government's use of corrective action during the "Made in China" product recall crisis. The government implemented stricter safety standards and enhanced regulatory measures to address concerns, which helped mitigate the negative impact on the nation's image. This case underscores how corrective action, when paired with transparency and commitment to long-term change, can lead to successful image repair.

Despite its advantages, corrective action requires a genuine commitment to change (Benoit, 1995a). If stakeholders perceive the action as superficial or insufficient, the strategy can backfire. Brazeal (2008) analyzed the failed image repair of former NFL star Terrell Owens, noting that the absence of any specific corrective actions in his public apologies diminished his credibility. Owens' failure to propose measures that would prevent future transgressions left his audience unconvinced of his sincerity, demonstrating that corrective action must be accompanied by a visible, genuine effort to be effective.

Corrective action is most effective when the offending party takes responsibility and implements meaningful changes that reassure stakeholders (Benoit, 2018c). While it may be challenging to execute, when done properly, corrective action can successfully restore trust and reputation (Benoit and Drew, 1997; Benoit, 2018c).

Materials and Methods

Participants

A total of 534 participants responded to a survey in August of 2023. Each participant was recruited through Amazon Mechanical Turk (MTurk) and offered a \$0.25 incentive for participating. Respondents were randomly assigned to one of 14 groups. Each group aligned with one of 14 image repair strategies including denial (N=29), shifting blame (N=22), provocation (N=35), defeasibility (N=35), accident (N=35), good intentions (N=32), bolstering (N=40), minimization (N=29), differentiation (N=39), transcendence (N=48), attacking accuser (N=34), compensation (N=53), corrective action (N=49), and mortification (N=54). Each respondent in the included sample spent at least two minutes on the survey and correctly responded to two reading checks.

All respondents were in the United States at the time the survey was taken, including 302 participants who were male (56.6%), 228 who were female (42.7%), and one who was either non-binary, a third gender, or preferred not to respond (0.2%). Race and age demographics can be found in Table 1. The sample included more white participants (91%) than what is reflected in the actual US population (75.5% according to US Census Bureau), and this is mentioned in the limitations section of the study.

Table 1 Participant Demographics

Race	White	486 (91.0%)
Age	Asian	27 (5.1%)
	Black or African American	11 (2.1%)
	American Indian or Alaska Native	5 (0.9%)
	Other (4) or missing (1)	5 (0.9%)
	18-24	64 (12.0%)
	25-34	224 (42.1%)
	35-44	188 (35.2%)
	45-54	27 (5.1%)
	55-64	22 (4.1%)
	65-74	6 (1.1%)
Missing	2 (0.003%)	

Data Collection Procedure

Participants who clicked on the MTurk job link were taken to an instruction page on the MTurk website. If they wanted to continue, they clicked on a Qualtrics link that led them to the survey. At the beginning of the survey, participants could read the informed consent message and decide whether to continue. If they decided to continue, they were shown a situation statement (see Table 2). All 14 groups were shown the same situation statement and corresponding reading check question. Next, each participant read a follow-up statement given by Bob, the hypothetical person in the situation being accused of misconduct. Again, a corresponding reading check question was shown alongside the statement. Each of the 14 groups had a unique follow-up statement that aligned with the image repair strategy of their group. These statements and the reading check are found below in the instrument section.

After reading both the situation statement and follow-up statement, all participants were given the same 28 questions measuring their perceptions of Bob and his attempt to repair his image. The 28 questions were shuffled randomly, giving each participant a unique item order. Upon completion of the 28 items, three more demographic questions were asked. Participants were then given a unique random ID that they copied and pasted into the MTurk webpage. This process confirmed their participation in the survey so that they could claim their incentive, thus completing their participation.

Instrument

142

Although Benoit's (1995a) typology categorizes message strategies employed by those in need of image repair, the present study focuses on audience perceptions that result from exposure to those strategies. Thus, this study does not attempt to test the internal structure of the image repair categories. The goal of the exploratory factor analysis was to identify latent perceptual dimensions that audiences may use when evaluating image repair attempts. In other words, Benoit's framework explains what speakers do rhetorically, whereas the present scale measures how audiences interpret and evaluate those rhetorical acts. Because image repair categories and audience perceptions operate at different theoretical levels, a one-to-one correspondence between the 14 strategies and the five perceptual subscales was not expected.

The first part of the survey instrument was the following hypothetical situation statement. *"Bob is a Vice President at Local University. A story just broke accusing him of misusing University funds for personal gain. If this is true, the allegations could cost Bob his job, reputation as a good-standing member of the community, and potentially much more."* The corresponding reading check asked, *"What is Bob being accused of?"* The options included, *"Misusing university funds for personal gain"* (the correct answer), *"Writing a story,"* and *"Some other accusation."* The reading check served as a sorting tool to ensure all included participants had read the statement.

The second part of the survey instrument included 14 statements the hypothetical character Bob made, following the initial accusation. Each statement and its corresponding reading check are available in Table 2.

Table 2 Bob's response to the accusation in all 14 scenarios

Strategy	Statement	Reading Check
Denial	I have been made aware of reports that I misused University funds. I emphatically deny these allegations. I have never inappropriately spent or transferred any money that I had access to as a University employee.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Emphatically deny the allegations (correct answer) A2. Accept responsibility
Shifting Blame	I have been made aware of reports that I misused University funds. I want to make it clear that I was not the employee responsible. If funds were misused, the mistakes made, either intentionally or unintentionally, were made by someone else.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Claim that he is not the employee responsible (Correct answer) A2. Accept responsibility
Provocation	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I would like to add some context addressing why some decisions were made. I have children who often provoked me, asking why they couldn't participate in certain recreational activities, go to concerts with their friends, etc. Wanting to be a good father, I did use some university funds to give them the quality of life that any parent would want for their children.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Said his children provoked him to do it (Correct answer) A2. Denied that it happened
Defeasibility	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I would like to make it very clear that each of the actions addressed in the reports were out of my control. The environment that we are expected to work in each day is disorganized and we are often working without the information that we need to make proper decisions.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Said that it was out of his control (Correct answer) A2. Apologized
Accident	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I would like to first acknowledge that the details of the report are correct. However, never did I intentionally make an unethical decision. The misplacement of money was simply an accident, and unfortunately the funds were misused.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Say that it was simply an accident (Correct answer) A2. Deny that it happened
Good intentions	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. However, what wasn't reported was the reason why I made the decisions that I did. My intent was never to inappropriately use the funds. In fact, I believe that when all the details come out, that all will see that I made decisions with the best of intentions.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Say that he had the best of intentions (Correct answer) A2. Say that he did it maliciously

Strategy	Statement	Reading Check
Bolstering	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. As I read the reports, I found it interesting that some information was left out. For example, our department has made great strides since I have been in charge. We have constantly turned a profit and exceeded each and every one of our goals as a team. Our department is in a much better position than it was before I got here.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Talk about the great things he has done (Correct answer) A2. Talk about the bad choices he made
Minimization	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I believe the reports have been exaggerated. The "misuse of funds," as the reports state, was nothing out of the ordinary. I believe that similar audits of similar departments across our campus and across the nation would reveal similar acts. Acts that quite frankly I don't think are that big of a deal.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Say that it isn't that big of a deal (Correct answer) A2. Apologize
Differentiation	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. While there are accuracies in the report, I think it's important that we put everything in context. Our university is currently putting out much bigger fires, including cases of abuse, racism, and violence. Quite frankly, I find it offensive that some people have made this such a big deal.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Compare his acts to worse acts like abuse, racism, and violence (Correct answer) A2. Deny that it happened
Transcendence	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I would like to first remind everyone that employees in education are some of the most underpaid. We are seeing our quality of life dwindle each year as inflation rises, and our salaries fail to increase at the same rate. It's no wonder then that we do whatever we can to help our own families.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Put the act in the context of underpaid employees (Correct answer) A2. Apologize for mistakes
Attacking accuser	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. The journalists responsible, as well as their "sources" have acted extremely irresponsibly. They accessed information they shouldn't have, and drew conclusions that were reckless. I hope that their employers, as well as their readers, take the appropriate actions against them.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Discredit the journalists (Correct answer) A2. Apologize
Compensation	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I understand the confusion and some people's dissatisfaction with my part in it. Because of this, I will be making a large donation to the University to be used as a scholarship for underprivileged students.	Q. What was Bob's strategy? A1. Compensate the university with scholarship money (Correct answer) A2. Deny that he did anything wrong

Strategy	Statement	Reading Check
Corrective Action	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I understand the negative reaction to these reports and would like to do my best to return things to the way they were. Therefore, I will personally pay back every penny that was misused, so that our budget is restored completely.	Q. What was Bob’s strategy? A1. Offer to pay back the misused money (Correct answer) A2. Deny that it happened
Mortification	I have been made aware of the reports that I misused University funds. I would like to start by confirming that I did in fact misuse funds. I am ashamed of my actions, and I will accept whatever consequences lie ahead. I vow to never do anything like this ever again. I ask for forgiveness from the community, my co-workers, and anyone that was impacted by my wrongful actions.	Q. What was Bob’s strategy? A1. Apologize (Correct answer) A2. Deny

The researchers created 28 items for this project based on many years of studying and applying image repair theory. Hypothetical examples of each strategy were developed using awareness of the way the strategy has been used before in numerous academic articles demonstrating the particular tactic. An attempt was made to avoid confusion and ambiguity by using clear examples of the strategies without blurring lines between them (e.g., compensation vs. corrective action; good intentions vs. transcendence; defeasibility vs. shifting blame). In particular, the mortification response is meant to reflect the prototypical conceptualization of this strategy (e.g., taking responsibility in any form), but also include elements of a more authentic mortification such as clearly identifying the misdeed, and asking for forgiveness without dictating the consequences. The questions were meant to measure intellectual conclusions a person might reach after hearing the individual image repair statements. Each item used a 6-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree). Of these items, 25 were used after an exploratory factor analysis. The results of this test as well as a list of the questions are found in Table 3. Finally, the instrument included three demographic questions asking participants to report their age, race, and gender.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed in SPSS statistics. A principal components exploratory factor analysis was conducted using the 28 items intended to measure perception outcomes. These results were used to create five different subscales. A reliability analysis was conducted on each of the five subscales and resulted in acceptable reliability (Table 3). Three of the items were not included in any of the five subscales because of poor fit according to both the factor analysis and reliability analysis. These removed items included “*I think other people are likely to believe Bob was remorseful,*” “*I find myself liking Bob,*” and “*Bob made a statement at the appropriate time.*”

Table 3

Subscale	Item	Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha
Learning	Bob seems embarrassed by his actions	.728	.818
	I think Bob learned his lesson	.554	
	I think Bob regrets his mistake	.760	
	I think Bob will change his behavior to avoid situations like this again	.617	
	I think that Bob regrets that the incident happened	.640	
Appropriateness	Bob is apologizing in the right place/method	.602	.839
	Bob is apologizing to the right people	.635	
	Bob specifically said what it is that he did wrong	.578	
	I think Bob was remorseful	.694	
	Bob specifically asks for forgiveness	.671	
Character	I think Bob was honest	.751	.851
	I think Bob was logical	.713	
	I find Bob's statement authentic	.686	
	I find Bob's statement sincere	.681	
	I think that Bob was convincing	.678	
Rectify	I find myself wanting Bob to be forgiven	.558	.874
	I think Bob's relationships should be completely restored	.615	
	I think Bob's reputation should be completely restored	.680	
	I think Bob's status should be completely restored	.724	
	I believe that the motive behind Bob's statement was genuine	.693	
Sincerity	Bob implies that he won't offer excuses	.508	.810
	Bob's statement is appropriate considering the offense	.612	
	Bob provides a strong justification for his actions	.700	
	Bob was specific when talking about his behavior	.540	
	I think Bob's statement truly reflects his own feelings	.509	

Once subscales were finalized, a MANCOVA was conducted with image repair strategy (14 levels) as the independent variable, the five subscales (Learning, Appropriateness,

Character, Rectification, and Sincerity) as dependent variables, and age, gender, and race entered as covariates. A MANCOVA was appropriate because the design included multiple correlated dependent variables that we wished to test simultaneously across the 14 image repair strategy conditions while controlling for covariates. This approach reduces Type I error compared to conducting separate ANCOVAs for each outcome.

Homogeneity of covariance matrices was examined with Box’s M test. Because this assumption was violated, Pillai’s Trace was used as the multivariate test statistic, given its robustness to unequal variances and sample sizes. Follow-up univariate ANCOVAs were inspected to determine whether image repair strategy significantly influenced each dependent variable. To probe group-level differences, Bonferroni-adjusted pairwise comparisons of estimated marginal means were conducted for each subscale. These comparisons focused on significant central contrasts involving mortification and corrective action relative to alternative strategies.

Results

Upon examining homogeneity of covariance matrices, it was noted that Box’s M was significant, Box’s $M = 342.41$, $F(195, 70191.38) = 1.62$, $p < .001$, indicating a violation of the assumption of equal covariance matrices. Accordingly, Pillai’s Trace was used as the multivariate test statistic. The multivariate effect of strategy on the combined dependent variables was significant, Pillai’s Trace = .24, $F(65, 1970) = 1.55$, $p = .003$, partial $\eta^2 = .05$. This indicates that the 14 strategies differed in their effects across the five subscales. Follow-up univariate ANCOVAs revealed significant effects of strategy on learning, $F(13, 394) = 2.75$, $p = .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .08$, appropriateness, $F(13, 394) = 3.38$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .10$, character, $F(13, 394) = 2.19$, $p = .010$, partial $\eta^2 = .07$, rectification, $F(13, 394) = 1.76$, $p = .047$, partial $\eta^2 = .06$, and sincerity, $F(13, 394) = 2.24$, $p = .008$, partial $\eta^2 = .07$.

Bonferroni-adjusted pairwise comparisons revealed several specific differences among strategies. For learning, mortification produced significantly higher evaluations than defeasibility ($p = .047$), bolstering ($p = .003$), and attacking the accuser ($p = .025$). For appropriateness, mortification again outperformed defeasibility ($p = .034$), bolstering ($p = .003$), transcendence ($p = .005$), and attacking the accuser ($p < .001$). Additionally, corrective action was significantly more effective than attacking the accuser ($p = .004$). The character subscale showed a nearly identical pattern. Mortification was rated higher than defeasibility ($p = .034$), bolstering ($p = .003$), transcendence ($p = .005$), and attacking the accuser ($p < .001$). For rectification, both mortification ($p = .026$) and corrective action ($p = .004$) received significantly higher scores than attacking the accuser. Finally, for sincerity, mortification again outperformed attacking the accuser ($p = .026$). Across subscales, mortification consistently yielded higher evaluations than several defensive strategies, while corrective action showed targeted advantages over attacking the accuser.

Table 4 Significant Pairwise Comparisons

DV	Pairwise Comparison	p
Learning	Mortification > Defeasibility	.047
	Mortification > Bolstering	.003
	Mortification > Attacking the Accuser	.025
Appropriateness	Mortification > Defeasibility	.034
	Mortification > Bolstering	.003
	Mortification > Transcendence	.005
	Mortification > Attacking the Accuser	<.001
	Corrective Action > Attacking the Accuser	.004
Character	Mortification > Defeasibility	.034
	Mortification > Bolstering	.003
	Mortification > Transcendence	.005
	Mortification > Attacking the Accuser	<.001
Rectification	Mortification > Attacking the Accuser	.026
	Corrective Action > Attacking the Accuser	.004
Sincerity	Mortification > Attacking the Accuser	.026

Discussion

Results from the learning subscale demonstrate that participants were more likely to believe the accused has learned from their mistakes if they used mortification as their primary strategy. Taking responsibility demonstrates an awareness of the harm caused as well as the accused’s role in creating the harm. Some strategies were not well connected to learning: bolstering (accused believes their good traits outweigh any harm done), defeasibility (blaming external causes does not show that the accused understands the full scope of the harm); and attacking the accuser (lashing out at others shows a lack of humility that runs counter to learning).

Moreover, results demonstrate that mortification is viewed as the most complete strategy because it matches with the recognized expectations for an apology (Stein and Barton, 2019), namely a representative (acknowledging what was done), expressive (showing regret and appropriate emotional response, sometimes referred to as contrition), and commissive (planning a course correction for the future) (Searle, 1975; Lee and Barton, 2003). The distinction between mortification and corrective action lies in the last of these three features, specifically the commissive expectation. Mortification prioritizes the explicit admission of wrongdoing and demonstrates contrition while making no direct attempt to

make demands on or steer the consequences toward any perception of a self-interested outcome. Thus, consequences are viewed as a natural outgrowth of the harm. Corrective action, on the other hand, often centers on pragmatic steps to address and prevent further harm, but may lack the emotional and moral weight of taking responsibility. Corrective action by itself can become problematic if executed without a clear acknowledgment of the harm caused, allowing individuals to appear proactive without fully accepting culpability. Such acts risk being perceived as superficial, particularly when corrective measures sidestep genuine remorse. Distinguishing between these approaches is essential to understanding their unique contributions and limitations in the image repair literature. While they often complement one another, treating corrective action as inherently separate from mortification can prevent oversimplification.

The results from the appropriateness subscale support the observation that mortification is the most complete strategy as well because participants felt that it was the most reasonable strategy under the circumstances. Ironically, while mortification is identified as the most complete strategy across the subscales, certain people seem to avoid this option at all costs. Some of the reasons could be potential legal entanglements (Benoit and Drew, 1997), job loss, damage to public or private face, or even personal pride. Accusations of cancel culture may also fuel a person’s desire to be less forthcoming about the reasons, motivations, and circumstances surrounding the actual act in question (Vogels et al., 2021).

Despite the altruistic pledge that comes from the definable and discernable characteristics of mortification, there is some evidence that corrective action magnifies the positive impact of mortification. Anyone can take responsibility, but taking actions beyond the words is that extra step that better encapsulates remorse. It is one thing to feel bad about something—and want to do better—but the accused can reach a higher character plane when they make tangible changes in their life (e.g., rehab, public advocacy) of their own volition. Such concrete changes also tie in with participant responses on the sincerity subscale, where they viewed corrective action as the primary strategy for demonstrating authenticity. One explanation for this result is that an apology is not deemed sincere unless there is an action that follows. In fact, when there is corrective action where a person has to engage in an overt behavior, it is perceived as more binding, and consequently more real. The literature on *antapologia* would support this idea, as one of the key strategies for rejecting an apologetic response is that an *apologia* is incomplete in part because of the lack of corrective action (Stein, 2008).

Results from several subscales also demonstrate the peril in using defeasibility as a strategy. Stein and Ostrowsky (2016) found that students predominantly used defeasibility in making excuses to their professors. They reference attribution theory to suggest that students would rather blame external circumstances than their own moral or ethical deficiencies. Similarly, the data from all subscales suggests that participants did not view blaming external causes as an acceptable accounting for behavior; it was viewed as a lazy strategy for deflecting blame and created negative assessments of character, sincerity, appropriateness, learning, and rectifying the situation. The conundrum revealed here is that you cannot simultaneously take responsibility while also ceding responsibility. Therefore, it makes sense that participants did not view defeasibility as an effective strategy.

A final observation evident in the data reveals that participants believe that attacking the accuser is the worst strategy available. Rooted in previous studies from Malloy and Pearson-Merkowitz (2016), there is a potential backlash from audiences toward an accused person employing attacks, thereby making them appear even worse. A common reason for this dissatisfaction is these statements are often overly emotional, rushed, and irrational. For example, Republican Representative Paul Gosar was the target of a vicious attack by his own siblings in a series of political ads. In response, he tweeted, “My siblings who chose to film ads against me are all liberal Democrats who all hate President Trump. These disgruntled Hilary supporters [sic] are related by blood to me [sic] but like leftists everywhere, they put political ideology before family. Stalin would be proud.” Such attacks make the person look impulsive, even immature, adding suspicion that there is more to the story than the accused is willing to admit. Thus, it is clear that this strategy should be avoided.

A Two-Pronged Approach

The findings of this study provide strong empirical support for the argument that mortification and corrective action are the most effective strategies for image repair. The mortification and corrective action stimulants consistently led to the perception that the accused had learned from their mistakes. This response aligns with societal expectations of sincere apologies, which demand accountability and humility (Stein and Barton, 2019). By acknowledging wrongdoing, mortification not only satisfies the public’s desire for fault admission, but also sets the stage for potential forgiveness and rehabilitation (Benoit, 2015).

150

This study also suggests that mortification, while powerful on its own, is most effective when paired with corrective action. Corrective action involves taking concrete steps to rectify the wrongdoing and prevent its recurrence, thereby signaling a commitment to change. These findings emphasize that the combination of these strategies was viewed as the most authentic and meaningful demonstration of remorse, enhancing the accused’s credibility and character. By addressing both the emotional and practical elements of the apology, this approach resonates with audiences who seek not only verbal regret, but also tangible signs of reform (Benoit and Brinson, 1994; Peijuan et al., 2009).

This two-pronged approach of an apology combined with corrective action proved to be more effective than strategies that deflect responsibility or avoid accountability. The preference for mortification and corrective action reflects broader social norms regarding the expectation of accountability and self-improvement. As participants indicated, while verbal apologies are sometimes seen as performative, the inclusion of corrective actions demonstrates genuine remorse and a desire to make amends, particularly when the follow-through can be easily observed or documented. The combined effect of these strategies elevates the accused’s character and reflects both personal and social commitment to responsibility.

These findings align with existing literature, which consistently shows that mortification and corrective action are critical for effective image restoration (Arendt et al., 2017; Benoit and Drew, 1997; Siew-Yoong Low et al., 2011). These strategies address both the emotional need for accountability and the practical demand for restitution, allowing

individuals and organizations to successfully navigate crises and restore their public image. By embracing both responsibility and reform, mortification and corrective action present the most comprehensive and authentic path to image restoration, thereby mitigating long-term reputational damage and fostering public trust.

Conclusion

Several limitations exist with this study, and are outlined here. First, although the findings provide strong empirical evidence to support the use of the mortification and corrective action strategies, they do not shed any additional light on why corporations or agents continue to use strategies that are deemed less effective by image repair theory. For example, why do the accused continue to use the attacking accuser strategy, when there is no evidence to support its efficacy? While past literature (Benoit, 2021) points to legal concerns, self-preservation, ego, or strategic delay, further evidence is needed to support these arguments, and that was outside the scope of the current study.

Second, both the use of a hypothetical scenario rather than a real image crisis, and the employment of an MTurk sample limit the generalizability and validity of the study. Real world image crises involve more contextual variables including reputation, identification, media framing, etc. Those variables cannot be captured in a hypothetical simulation. Because of this, future research should use the scale against real word scenarios and measure the variables listed. Future research could also fine tune the scale and also add variables and constructs that could further explain audience perceptions of image repair strategies.

This study enhances our knowledge of the impact of various image repair strategies by establishing a reliable scale for measuring audience’s reactions to *apologia* efforts both real and hypothetical. Strategies like mortification and corrective action that are more forthright, open, and willing to make change are more palatable to audiences in most circumstances. On the contrary, strategies that attempt to justify, minimize or deflect blame, are easily discerned by audiences as weaker strategies, yet surprisingly, people continue to use them (Benoit and Drew, 1997). Making more specific one-to-one connections between strategy and response can provide greater understanding for academics as well as practitioners about which image repair strategies fit best in unique cases.

References

- Arendt, C., LaFleche, M., and Limperopulos, M. A. (2017). A qualitative meta-analysis of apologia, image repair, and crisis communication: Implications for theory and practice. *Public Relations Review*, 43(3), 517-526.
- Benoit, W. L. (1982). Richard M. Nixon’s rhetorical strategies in his public statements on Watergate. *Southern Speech Communication Journal*, 47, 192-211.

- Benoit, W. L. (1995a). *Accounts, excuses, and apologies: A theory of image restoration strategies*. State University of New York Press.
- Benoit, W. L. (1995b). Sears' repair of its auto service image: Image restoration discourse in the corporate sector. *Communication Quarterly*, 46, 89-105.
- Benoit, W. L. (1997). Hugh Grant's image restoration discourse: An actor apologizes. *Communication Quarterly*, 45, 251-268.
- Benoit, W. L. (2011). NPR's image repair discourse on firing Juan Williams. *Journal of Radio and Audio Media*, 18, 84-91.
- Benoit, W. L. (2016a). Effects of image repair strategies. *Putting image repair to the test: Quantitative applications of image restoration theory*, 7-28
- Benoit, W. L. (2016b). Barack Obama's 2008 speech on Reverend Wright: Defending self and others. *Public Relations Review*, 42, 843-848. Doi: 10.1016/j.pubrev.2016.09.003
- Benoit, W. L. (2017). Image repair on the Donald Trump "Access Hollywood" video: "Grab them by the p*ssy." *Communication Studies*, 68, 243-259.
- Benoit, W. L. (2018a). Roger Goodell's image repair on the Ray Rice suspension. *Relevant Rhetoric*, 9, 1-21.
- Benoit, W. L. (2018b). Production of image repair strategies in the 2016 American presidential debates. *Langage and société*, 2, 25-38.
- Benoit, W. L. (2018c). Crisis and Image Repair at United Airlines: Fly the Unfriendly Skies. *Journal of International Crisis and Risk Communication Research*, 1(1), 11-26.
- Benoit, W. L. (2019). John F. Kennedy's image repair on "The Catholic Issue" in the 1960 West Virginia presidential primary. *American Communication Journal*, 21, 1-10.
- Benoit, W. (2021, November 29). Image Repair in Crisis Communication. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics*. Retrieved 19 Feb. 2026, from <https://oxfordre.com/politics/view/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.001.0001/acrefore-9780190228637-e-1593>.
- Benoit, W. L., and Anderson, K. K. (1996). Blending politics and entertainment: Dan Quayle versus Murphy Brown. *Southern Communication Journal*, 62, 73-85.
- Benoit, W. L., and Brinson, S. L. (1994). ATandT: "Apologies are not enough." *Communication Quarterly*, 42, 75-88.
- Benoit, W. L., and Czerwinski, A. (1997). A critical analysis of USAir's image repair discourse. *Business Communication Quarterly*, 60, 38-58.
- Benoit, W. L., and Drew, S. (1997). Appropriateness and effectiveness of image restoration strategies. *Communication Reports*, 10, 153-163.
- Benoit, W. L., Gullifor, P., and Panici, D., (1991). Reagan's discourse on the Iran-Contra affair. *Communication Studies*, 42, 272-294.
- Benoit, W. L., and Henson, J. R. (2009). President Bush's image repair discourse on Hurricane Katrina. *Public Relations Review*, 35, 40-46. Doi: 10.1016/j.pubrev.2008.09.022
- Benoit, W. L., and Hanczor, R. S. (1994). The Tonya Harding controversy: An analysis of image restoration strategies. *Communication Quarterly*, 42, 120-140.
- Benoit, W. L., and Lindsey, J. J. (1987). Argument strategies: Antidote to Tylenol's poisoned image. *Journal of the American Forensic Association*, 23, 136-46.
- Benoit, W. L., and Nill, D. M. (1998). Oliver Stone's defense of JFK. *Communication Quarterly*, 46, 127-143.
- Bitzer, L. F. (1968). The rhetorical situation. *Philosophy and Rhetoric*, 1, 1-14.
- Blair, C. (1984). From *All the President's Men* to every man for himself: The strategies of post-Watergate *apologia*. *Central States Speech Journal*, 35, 250-260.

Braden Hale Bagley
Kevin A. Stein
Matthew H. Barton
Hayden V. Coombs

“No Excuses: An Empirical Case for Mortification
and Corrective Action”

- Brazeal, L. M. (2008). The image repair strategies of Terrell Owens. *Public Relations Review*, 34(2), 145-150.
- Brinson, S. L., and Benoit, W. L. (1996). Dow Corning's image repair strategies in the breast implant crisis. *Communication Quarterly*, 44, 29-41.
- Brown, K. A. (2016). Is apology the best policy? An experimental examination of the effectiveness of image repair strategies during criminal and noncriminal athlete transgressions. *Communication and Sport*, 4(1), 23-42.
- Compton, J. (2014). Arby's image repair tactics as a public relations strategy. *Public Relations Review*, 40, 122-124.
- Compton, J., and Miller, B. (2011). Image repair in late night comedy: Letterman and the Palin joke controversy. *Public Relations Review*, 37, 415-421.
- Drumheller, K., and Benoit, W. L. (2004). USS Greenville collides with Japan's Ehime Maru: Cultural issues in image repair discourse. *Public Relations Review*, 30, 177-185.
- Edwards, J. A. (2005). Community-focused *apologia* in international affairs: Japanese Prime Minister Tomiichi Murayama's apology. *Howard Journal of Communication*, 16(4), 317-336.
- Edwards, J. A. (2008). The mission of healing: Kofi Annan's failed apology. *Atlantic Journal of Communication*, 16, 88-104.
- Ferguson, D. P., Wallace, J. D., and Chandler, R. C. (2018). Hierarchical consistency of strategies in image repair theory: PR practitioners' perceptions of effective and preferred crisis communication strategies. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 30(5-6), 251-272.
- Frederick, E. L., Burch, L. M., Sanderson, J., and Hambrick, M. E. (2014). To invest in the invisible: A case study of Manti Te'o's image repair strategies during the Katie Couric interview. *Public Relations Review*, 780-788.
- Glantz, M. (2010). The Floyd Landis doping scandal: Implications for image repair discourse. *Public Relations Review*, 36(2), 157-163.
- Gribas, J., DiSanza, J. R., Hartman, K. L., Carr, D. J., and Legge, N. J. (2021). Exploring the effectiveness of image repair tactics: Comparison of U.S. and Middle Eastern audiences. *Communication Research Reports*, 38(3), 150-160.
- Handley, R. L. (2008). Israeli image repair: Recasting the deviant actor to retell the story. *Journal of Communication Inquiry*, 32(2), 140-154.
- Harlow, W. F., Brantley, B. C., and Harlow, R. M. (2011). BP initial image repair strategies after the Deepwater Horizon spill. *Public Relations Review*, 37(1), 80-83.
- Harrell, J., Ware, B. L., and Linkugel, W. A. (1975). Failure of apology in American politics: Nixon on Watergate. *Speech Monographs*, 42, 245-261.
- Hearit, K. M. (1999). Newsgroups, activist publics, and corporate *apologia*: The case of Intel and its Pentium chip. *Public Relations Review*, 25, 291-308.
- Hindman, E. B. (2005). Jayson Blair, *The New York Times*, and paradigm repair. *Journal of Communication*, 55(2), 225-241.
- Husselbee, L. P., and Stein, K. A. (2012). In the rough: Tiger Woods' apology and journalistic *antapologia*. *Journal of Sports Media*, 7(1), 59-87.
- Huxman, S. S., and Bruce, D. B. (1995). Toward a dynamic generic framework of *apologia*: A case study of Dow Chemical, Vietnam, and the napalm controversy. *Communication Studies*, 46, 57-72.
- Kahl, M. (1984). Blind ambition culminates in lost honor: A comparative analysis of John Dean's apologetic strategies. *Central States Speech Journal*, 35, 239-250.
- Kauffman, J. (2012). Hooray for Hollywood? The 2011 Golden Globes and Ricky Gervais' image repair strategies. *Public Relations Review*, 38(1), 46-50.

- Kauffman, J. (2018). My ego made me do it: The image repair strategies of Brian Williams. *Northwest Journal of Communication*, 46(1), 87-107.
- Kaylor, B. (2010). In the eye of the storm: Image repair discourse of Dan Rather and CBS after the Bush Guard memos story. *Southwestern Mass Communication Journal*, 26(1), 111-124.
- Kennedy, K. A., and Benoit, W. L. (1997). The Newt Gingrich book deal controversy: Self-defense rhetoric. *Southern Communication Journal*, 63, 197-216.
- Kramer, M. R. (2013). Image repair rhetoric and shock radio: Don Imus, Al Sharpton, and the Rutgers women's basketball team controversy. *Journal of Radio and Audio Media*, 21(2), 247-257.
- Kramer, M. R., and Olson, K. M. (2002). The strategic potential of sequencing *apologia* stases: President Clinton's self-defense in the Monica Lewinsky scandal. *Western Journal of Communication*, 66, 347-367.
- Lauzen, M. M. (2016). Image repair: A case study of Thierry Fremaux and the Cannes Film Festival. *Public Relations Review*, 42(1), 170-175.
- Lee, R., and Barton, M. H. (2003). Clinton's rhetoric of contrition. In R. E. Denton and R. L. Holloway (Eds.), *Images, scandal and communication strategies of the Clinton Presidency* (pp. 219-246). Praeger.
- Len-Ríos, M. E. (2010). Image repair strategies, local news portrayals and crisis stage: A case study of Duke University's lacrosse team crisis. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 4(4), 267-287.
- Len-Ríos, M. E., and Benoit, W. L. (2004). Gary Condit's image repair strategies: Determined denial and differentiation. *Public Relations Review*, 30, 95-106.
- Len-Ríos, M. E., Finneman, T., Han, K. J., Bhandari, M., Perry, E. L. (2015). Image repair campaign strategies addressing race: Paula Deen, social media, and defiance. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 9(2), 148-165.
- Liu, B. F. (2008). From aspiring presidential candidate to accidental racist? An analysis of Senator George Allen's image repair during his 2006 reelection campaign. *Public Relations Review*, 34, 331-336.
- Maehle, N., and Supphellen, M. (2015). Advertising strategies for brand image repair: The effectiveness of advertising alliances. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 21(6), 450-462.
- Malloy, L. C., and Pearson-Merkowitz, S. (2016). Going positive: The effects of negative and positive advertising on candidate success and voter turnout. *Research and Politics*, 1-15.
- Martin, S., and McHendry, Jr., (2016). Kaepernick's stand: Patriotism, protest, and professional sports. *Journal of Contemporary Rhetoric*, 6(3/4), 88-98.
- McClearey, K. (1983). Audience effects of *apologia*. *Communication Quarterly*, 31(1), 12-20.
- McGuire, J. (2012). Excellence in broadcasting: Rush Limbaugh and image repair in the Sandra Fluke controversy. *Journal of Radio and Audio Media*, 19(2), 206-220.
- Moody, M. (2011). Jon and Kate Plus 8: A case study of social media and image repair tactics. *Public Relations Review*, 37(4), 405-414.
- Mueller II, A. G. (2004). Affirming denial through preemptive *apologia*: The case of the Armenian genocide resolution. *Western Journal of Communication*, 68(1), 24-44.
- Nelson, J. (1984). The defense of Billie Jean King. *Western Journal of Communication*, 48, 92-102.
- Ostrowsky, M. K., and Stein, K. A. (2020). "They executed better than we did": Image repair strategies used by athletes who lost big games. *Journal of Sports Media*, 15(1), 75-97.
- Page, T. G. (2019). Beyond attribution: Building new measures to explain the reputation threat posed by crisis. *Public Relations Review*, 45, 138-152.
- Peijuan, C., Ting, L. P., and Pang, A. (2009). Managing a nation's image during crisis: A study of the Chinese government's image repair efforts in the "Made in China" controversy. *Public Relations Review*, 35(3), 213-218.

Braden Hale Bagley
Kevin A. Stein
Matthew H. Barton
Hayden V. Coombs

“No Excuses: An Empirical Case for Mortification
and Corrective Action”

- Riggs, R. (2019). A new season for the Baylor Nation: Image repair and organizational learning. *Ohio Communication Journal*, 57, 33-46.
- Sanderson, J., and Hambrick, M. E. (2016). Riding along with Lance Armstrong: Exploring antapologia in response to athlete adversity. *Journal of Sports Media*, 11(1), 1-24.
- Searle, J. R. (1975). A taxonomy of illocutionary acts. In K. Gunderson (Ed.), *Language, mind and knowledge* (pp. 344-369). University of Minnesota Press.
- Seeger, M. W., and Ulmer, R. R. (2002). A post-crisis discourse of renewal: The cases of Malden Mills and Cole Hardwoods. *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 30, 126-142.
- Sheffer, M. L., Schultz, B., and Tubbs, W. (2018). #deflategate. *Newspaper Research Journal*, 39(1), 69-82.
- Sheldon, C. A., and Sallot, L. M. (2009). Image repair in politics: Testing effects of communication strategy and performance history in a faux pas. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 21(1), 25-50.
- Shmittel, A., and Hull, K. (2015). “Shit Got Cray Cray #MYBAD”: An examination of the image repair discourse of Richie Incognito during the Miami Dolphins’ bullying scandal. *Journal of Sports Media*, 10(2), 115-137.
- Short, B. (1987). Comic book *apologia*: The “paranoid” rhetoric of Congressman George Hansen. *Western Journal of Communication*, 51, 189-203.
- Siew-Yoong Low, Y., Varughese, J., and Pang, A. (2011). Communicating crisis: How culture influences image repair in Western and Asian governments. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 16(3), 218-242.
- Simons, H. W. (2000). A dilemma-centered analysis of Clinton’s August 17th *apologia*: Implications for rhetorical theory. *Quarterly Journal of Speech*, 86, 438-454.
- Smith, E. (2012). Corporate image and public health: An analysis of the Philip Morris, Kraft, and Nestle websites. *Journal of Health Communication*, 17, 582-600.
- Smith, J. S. (2017). “Convenience,” “Short-circuited,” and October surprise: An analysis of Hillary Clinton’s progressive *apologia* during the email server scandal. *Kentucky Journal of Communication*, 36(1), 4-34.
- Sng, K., and Au, T. Y. (2019). Social media influencers as a crisis risk in strategic communication: Impact of discretions on professional endorsements. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 13(4), 301-320.
- Sohn, Y. J., and Edwards, H. H. (2018). Strategic ambiguity and crisis *apologia*: The impact of audiences’ interpretation of mixed messages. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 12(5), 552-570.
- Stein, K. A. (2008). *Apologia, antapologia* and the 1960 Soviet U-2 Spy Plane incident. *Communication Studies*, 59, 19-34.
- Stein, K. A. (2010). Jewish *antapologia* in response to Mel Gibson’s multiple attempts at absolution. *Relevant Rhetoric*, 1, 1-14.
- Stein, K. A., and Barton, M. H. (2019). “I’m sorry you interpreted my behavior the way you did”: Toward a new understanding of the nuances of mortification. *Western Journal of Communication*, 83(2), 252-264.
- Stein, K. A., Barton, M. H., Ault, M., and Briscoe, J. R. (2013). Apologist-in-Chief?: Newspaper *kategoria* and *antapologia* following Barack Obama’s “Global Apology Tour”. *Iowa Communication Journal*, 45, 39-63.
- Stein, K. A., Barton, M. H., and Pierson, K. (2021). “It was like I had murdered a baby”: Hollywood filmmakers’ *apologia* following “bad” films. *Ohio Journal of Communication*, 59, 17-31.
- Stein, K. A., and Ostrowsky, M. K. (2016). “Taco the Puppy is super sick”: Student excuses as a unique form of *apologia* rhetoric. *Relevant Rhetoric*, 7, 1-19.

- Swanson, E. A. (2008). *Mortification as a crisis response strategy in hospital malpractice situations: A content analysis of www.sorryworks.net* (Doctoral dissertation). University of Georgia.
- Tabak, L., and Avraham, E. (2018). Country image repair strategies during an asymmetrical conflict: An analysis of the Gaza conflict in 2014. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 12(3), 237-251.
- Theye, K. (2008). Shoot, I'm sorry: An examination of narrative functions and effectiveness within Dick Cheney's hunting accident *apologia*. *Southern Communication Journal*, 73(2), 160-177.
- Thomsen, S. R. (2023). "Not the company we thought it was." Southwest Airlines' attempt at image repair during its October 2021 flight cancellation. *Public Relations Review*, 49(2), 102309.
- Vogels, E. A., Anderson, M., Porteus, M., Baronavsky, C., Atske, S., McClain, C., Auxier, B., Perrin, A., and Ramshankar, M. (2021, May 19). Americans and "Cancel Culture": Where some see calls for accountability, others see censorship, punishment. *Pew Research Center*. <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2021/05/19/americans-and-cancel-culture-where-some-see-calls-for-accountability-others-see-censorship-punishment/>
- Walsh, J., McAllister-Spooner, S. M. (2011). Analysis of the image repair discourse in the Michael Phelps controversy. *Public Relations Review* 37(2), 157-162.
- Wang, R., and Lewis, N. (2021). How do moral values and crisis response strategies influence individuals' evaluations and support of sports organizations post-crisis? *Crisis and Politics*, 98(3), 875-895.
- Ware, B. L., and Linkugel, W. A. (1973). They spoke in defense of themselves: On the generic criticism of *apologia*. *Quarterly Journal of Speech*, 59, 273-283.
- Wen, W., Yu, T., and Benoit, W. L. (2012). The failure of 'scientific' evidence in Taiwan: A case study of international image repair for American beef. *Asian Journal of Communication*, 22(2), 121-139.
- Wetherbee, B. (2019). "Redemption follows allocution": Dan Harmon and the #MeToo apology. *Journal of Contemporary Rhetoric*, 9(3/4), 112-125.
- Zhang, J. and Benoit, W. L. (2004). Message strategies of Saudi Arabia's image restoration campaign after 9/11. *Public Relations Review*, 30, 161-167.